

Synthesis of Tetrahydroxanthenes.

BY MANMOHAN SEN.

In the condensation of β -ketic esters with phenols there are two possible courses, one leading to the formation of coumarins (Pechmann's reaction) and the other to chromones (Simonis' reac-

tion). The work of Baker and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1981, 2349) and of Bargellini (*Gazzetta*, 1925, 55, 945) clearly prove that under Pechmann's conditions the condensation, contrary to the claims of Jacobsen and Ghosh, leads to coumarins irrespective of the nature of the β -ketic ester employed.

Sen and Basu (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 467) condensed ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate with phenols to note if a cyclic β -ketic ester (in which the reactive methine group is situated in the nucleus) have any influence in changing the course of the reaction. The products exhibited extraordinary stability towards alkalis and Sen and Basu were uncertain at first if these were coumarins (I) or chromones (II). They decided ultimately in favour of the coumarin structure as 2-cyanocyclohexanone gave identical products. Sonn (*Ber.*, 1918, 51, 1829) and Bargellini and Forli-Forti (*Gazzetta*, 1911, 41, 747) observed that cyano-ketones of the

types $\text{CN}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{R}$ on condensation with phenols invariably yield coumarins and not chromones.

In view of this there could not be left any doubt about the coumarin structure (I) assigned by Sen and Basu. It was thought however that conclusive evidence would be obtained by the synthesis of the corresponding tetrahydroxanthones (II).

Initial efforts to condense ethyl *o*-methoxybenzoate with *cyclohexanone* by means of sodium gave unsatisfactory results. It may be mentioned that Edouard Bauer (*Ann. Chim.*, 1914, (ix), 1, 393) obtained benzoyl *cyclohexanone* in very poor yield from ethyl benzoate and *cyclohexanone*. The condensation succeeded better with *o*-acetoxy benzoyl chlorides and sodio-*cyclohexanones*.

o-Acetoxy benzoyl *cyclohexanones* (III) were first formed from which on heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid the tetrahydroxanthones (II) were obtained. This method follows an unambiguous course and leaves no doubt about the xanthone structure of the products. The yields however were not satisfactory as side reactions, particularly the formation of diacylcyclohexanones, took place and the unaltered *cyclohexanones* (specially *p*-methylcyclohexanone which is insoluble in water) greatly hindered the isolation of the products in the solid form. Different procedures were therefore followed with *cyclohexanone* and *p*-methylcyclohexanone in isolating the products.

Reduced xanthones had not been described before and the tetrahydroxanthones obtained here are the only representatives of the class. While xanthones have high melting points these reduced bodies are quite low melting. They are crystalline substances and are extremely soluble in all organic solvents excepting ligroin. They do not form, like xanthones and chromones, oxonium salts. Even perchlorates could not be isolated though perchloric acid is the most useful reagent for obtaining stable salts of weak bases. (Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 178). The non-formation of oxonium salts is due obviously to the presence of the reduced ring. The influence of reduced rings on the basic character of oxygen has been amply demonstrated by the work of Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1588). The tetrahydroxanthones were readily hydrolysed by alkalis to *o*-hydroxy acids and *cyclohexanones*, so much so that the intermediate *o*-hydroxy benzoyl *cyclohexanones* (IV) could not be isolated.

7-Methyltetrahydroxanthone (V) was synthesised from acetyl *m*-cresotyl chloride and sodiocyclohexanone. It melted at 110°. Sen and Basu's compound from *m*-cresol and *cyclohexanone*-2-carboxylate had *m.p.* 119° and therefore could only be (VI).

This proves conclusively that the products obtained by Sen and Basu are really coumarins (I) and not chromones (II). Hence cyclic β -ketoic esters also condense with phenols in the usual manner. This establishes beyond dispute the general character of Pechmann's reaction and shows that in the condensation of β -ketoic esters with phenols the course of the reaction depends entirely on the nature of the condensing agent and is quite independent of the nature of the β -ketoic esters employed. Coumarins readily dissolve in alkalis on warming by the opening up of the lactonic ring. The peculiar stability of the coumarins of Sen and Basu therefore must be due to the presence of the reduced benzene ring, fused in 3:4-position of the coumarins.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Tetrahydroxanthone.—Molecular sodium (0.7 g.) suspended in dry ether (40 c.c.) was gradually treated with an ethereal solution (10 c.c.) of *cyclohexanone* (3 g.). The sodium gradually disappeared and the sodium salt of *cyclohexanone* separated out. When the reaction was over, the flask was cooled with ice and acetyl salicylyl chloride (6 g.) dissolved in ether (20 c.c.) was slowly introduced. After refluxing on the water-bath for 6 hours, cold dilute hydrochloric acid was added and the ethereal layer thoroughly washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution. On evaporating off the ether

a heavy oil was obtained which was boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid for an hour. The oily product was taken up in ether and washed with dilute alkali. On removing the ether a solid crystalline mass contaminated with some oil was obtained. It was dried on a porous plate and crystallised from petrol ether. Tetrahydroxanthone was obtained as rhombic cubes, m.p. 105°. It is very soluble in alcohol, benzene, ethyl acetate, acetone and ether, fairly soluble in benzine, and less so in petrol ether. It does not form a hydrochloride. Efforts at obtaining the perchlorate also gave no positive results. (Found: C, 77.87; H, 6.21. $C_{13}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 78.00; H, 6.0 per cent.)

6-Methyltetrahydroxanthone.—Sodiocyclohexanone (from .07 g. sodium and 3 g. cyclohexanone) was condensed as above with acetyl *p*-cresotyl chloride (6 g.) to form 6-methyltetrahydroxanthone. It crystallised from ligroin in elongated needles, m.p. 113°. Its solubility in different organic solvents resembled that of the previous compound. (Found: C, 78.38; H, 6.72. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 78.5; H, 6.54 per cent.)

7-Methyltetrahydroxanthone was prepared as before from sodiocyclohexanone and acetyl *m*-cresotyl chloride. On purification from petrol ether thin scales, m.p. 100° were deposited. (Found: C, 78.41; H, 6.66. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 78.5; H, 6.54 per cent.)

3-Methyltetrahydroxanthone.—To an ethereal suspension of sodiocyclohexanone (from 7 g. sodium and 3.4 g. of the ketone) an ethereal solution of acetyl salicyl chloride (6 g.) was added gradually with ice-cooling. After heating on the water-bath for six hours the intermediate compound was extracted out with dilute caustic soda solution and precipitated from the alkaline solution with ice-cold dilute acetic acid as a thick oil. This was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid for an hour. The oily product was washed in ethereal solution with cold dilute alkali when it was obtained as a semi-solid mass on evaporation of the ether. After drying on a porous plate it was crystallised from petrol ether, rectangular plates, m.p. 130-131° being deposited. (Found: C, 78.33; H, 6.81. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 78.5; H, 6.54 per cent.)

3:6-Dimethyltetrahydroxanthone.—Sodio-*p*-methylcyclohexanone and acetyl *p*-cresotyl chloride gave 3:6-dimethyltetrahydroxanthone, which separated from petrol ether as needles, m.p. 137-138°.

(Found: C, 79.09; H, 7.26. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 78.95; H, 7.00 per cent.).

3:7-Dimethyltetrahydroxanthone was obtained from sodio-*p*-methyl cyclohexanone and acetyl *m*-cresotyl chloride and recrystallised from ligroin. M.p. 118-119°. (Found: C, 78.81; H, 7.23. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 78.95; H, 7.00 per cent.).

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UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

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